

The Impact of Teacher Competency, Transformational Leadership of School Principals, and Organizational Culture on Teacher Performance

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ABSTRACT

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This study examines the impact of teacher competency, transformational leadership of school principals, and organizational culture on teacher performance. The objectives of this research are to analyze: (1) the effect of teacher competency on teacher performance, (2) the effect of transformational leadership of school principals on teacher performance, (3) the effect of organizational culture on teacher performance, and (4) the combined effect of teacher competency, transformational leadership of school principals, and organizational culture on teacher performance. The research method used is a survey. The research was conducted in Madrasah Aliyah based in Pesantren in the South Halmahera district with a sample of 25 teachers. Data analysis utilized simple regression analysis and multiple regression analysis. The results of the study indicate that: (1) there is a positive and significant influence of teacher competency on teacher performance with an F-value of 51.317 and a significance level less than 0.05, (2) there is a positive and significant influence of transformational leadership of school principals on teacher performance with an F-value of 51.792 and a significance level less than 0.05, (3) there is a positive and significant influence of organizational culture on teacher performance with an F-value of 86.576 and a significance level less than 0.05, and (4) there is a positive and significant combined influence of teacher competency, transformational leadership of school principals, and organizational culture on teacher performance with an F-value of 75.208 and a significance level less than 0.05. The influence of organizational culture is greater compared to teacher competency and transformational leadership of school principals.

KEYWORDS:

Teacher Performance, Teacher Competence, Transformational leadership, Organizational culture

1. INTRODUCTION

Employee performance, including that of teachers, plays a crucial role in every organization, including educational institutions (schools), because every organization aims to achieve the best employee performance. Teacher performance is a key determinant of educational quality, as teachers' work that aligns with the achievement of the desired educational vision, mission, goals, and targets will impact student learning and outcomes (Alfredo, T.R & Prijanto, B. 2022). Teacher performance is highly related to teacher

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competency, school principal leadership, organizational culture, and various other supporting factors. Teacher performance is considered very influential in determining student success, hence an educational institution requires teachers who have competencies relevant to their duties and responsibilities (Lavoué et al., 2019; Safitri et al., 2019). Teacher competency encompasses various abilities of teachers, including knowledge, skills, and attitudes, which are manifested in intelligent actions to perform their duties (Samerkhanova & Imzharova, 2018; Arifin, 2015). A competent or professional teacher understands how to behave and implement the knowledge and skills they possess (Wardoyo & Herdiani, 2017). Teacher performance is related to the leadership style of the school principal, hence the principal must ensure that teachers working under their leadership are satisfied with their profession and have a high commitment to the organization. Numerous studies have

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proven that employees or teachers with high performance and job satisfaction will demonstrate loyalty to their organization (Hoyt, 2012; Salehi & Gholtash, 2011; Lim, 2010; Gokce, 2013). Teacher performance in schools, especially in madrasahs on Bacan Island, varies from one to another. This is because each school has a principal with a different leadership style and a distinct organizational culture. Madrasah Aliyah on Bacan Island exhibits diversity, with some madrasahs implementing only the government-mandated curriculum and others being pesantren-based madrasahs that, in addition to the general curriculum, also incorporate pesantren activities. Most principals, particularly those of pesantren-based madrasahs, adopt either transactional or transformational leadership styles.

Previous studies examining teacher performance influenced by leadership styles, teacher competency, and organizational culture have been widely conducted. For instance, Rosdiana et al., 2023 stated that school principal leadership and organizational culture affect teacher performance. Other research also indicates that teacher performance is influenced by the transformational leadership of school principals (Astuty, W., et al., 2023; Burhanudin, & Saputri, 2023). The study by Halimahturrafiah et al. (2023) concluded that teacher competency significantly impacts teacher performance, meaning that an increase in teacher competency leads to a significant improvement in teacher performance. Furthermore, the study by Ritonga, et al. (2023) concluded that teacher competency and organizational culture positively influence teacher performance, implying that better teacher competency and organizational culture result in better teacher performance. Haryono et al. (2020) in their research concluded that school principal leadership and teacher competency positively affect teacher performance. These findings indicate that teacher performance can be enhanced by improving and changing the leadership style of school principals and increasing teacher competency.

In general, teacher performance is the most crucial and significant element in educational institutions (schools). This is because teacher performance in a school is directed toward teachers' behavior in carrying out their teaching duties. Teachers are responsible for providing quality education to students, which directly impacts their academic achievement. Teacher performance is also defined as the totality of a teacher's work to achieve the learning objectives planned for each instructional session (Suhaimi, 2018). Teacher performance is the result of work derived from the execution of their duties and responsibilities to achieve the goals of an educational institution (Weto et al (2020); Azizah et al., 2019). Normianti, et al. (2019) and Kartini, et al. (2020) concluded that teacher performance is defined as the tangible and measurable outcomes of a teacher's work. Teacher performance is the entirety of a teacher's work in the learning process to achieve objectives.

A teacher's competency is a set of knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values that a teacher must possess to perform their duties effectively and professionally (Rismawan, 2017; Rismawan & Saluy, 2018). Furthermore, Karlen et al. (2023) state that teacher competency is the ability or expertise that teachers must have to fulfill their duties and responsibilities as educators. Competent teachers must have a deep understanding of the subjects they teach, skills in designing and implementing instruction, and a professional attitude in interacting with students, parents, and colleagues. Quality teachers must possess the knowledge and understanding to adapt teaching methods/strategies/approaches to suit the interests and characteristics of students to achieve learning objectives.

Teachers must be able to motivate and inspire students in the classroom, help develop their social and emotional skills, and create a safe and inclusive learning environment for all students (Lestari et al., 2023). Competence is an important aspect that becomes a person's characteristics, namely the causes related to his reference criteria effective performance. such as (Lauda et al., 2019; Verma, 2020), explaining that talking about teacher competency cannot be separated from existing job requirements. Competencies can take the form of knowledge, skills, attitudes and behavior.

Teachers play a crucial role in the education system, shaping students' minds and preparing them for the future (Gheith & Aljaberi, 2018). To ensure their effectiveness, teachers need to participate in various continuous professional training and development programs (Tampang & Wonggo, 2018). This is intended to ensure that teachers keep up with the latest developments in teaching methods and educational theories, enabling them to provide high-quality instruction to their students. Continuous professional training and development help teachers acquire new skills, gain relevant knowledge, and enhance their teaching methodologies. By attending workshops, seminars, and conferences, teachers can broaden their understanding of subject matter and teaching strategies. Teachers with strong competencies tend to achieve better performance.

Leadership plays a crucial role in driving organizational change and achieving success in the digital era. Leadership is pivotal in shaping the direction and success of any organization, including educational institutions (Sahana, 2018). Transformational leadership is one of the leadership styles among various leadership styles. Transformational leadership demonstrates a significant effect on subordinates to motivate them to perform their tasks to the fullest (Omar & Husin, 2013). Transformational leadership is a leadership concept focused on organizational change and growth. School principals who implement transformational leadership are characterized by their ability to formulate a strong and inspirational vision for the school. A clear and meaningful vision can inspire students to adopt positive values and develop good character. Through a

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transformational leadership style, school principals can create positive changes in the school's culture and performance. This involves nurturing individuals, fostering creativity, and empowering school members to achieve higher educational goals. The concept of transformational leadership has been extensively studied in the field of educational leadership. Various research results indicate that transformational leadership has a positive impact on school quality, teacher work effectiveness, program quality, and student achievement.

Some of the research results, such as those by Hidayat et al. (2023), concluded that teacher performance can be enhanced with the transformational leadership style of school principals. Doutel et al., 2023; Sirait et al., 2021) concluded in their research that school principals play a highly strategic role as leaders, and selecting the transformational leadership style will impact the development of teacher performance towards improvement.

Work culture is a set of values, norms, and behaviors practiced in the work environment of an organization to create a harmonious, effective, and productive work atmosphere (Christin et al., 2019; Fitria, 2018; Juanda et al., 2023). Organizational culture refers to the basic assumptions and beliefs shared by members of an organization and is a consistent solution that can function well for a group in addressing external and internal problems (Williams et al., 2007). Previous research related to this study show that organizational culture has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance. This means that a strong and positive organizational culture can enhance teacher performance in schools, making it important for schools to strengthen a positive organizational culture to create a conducive work environment for teachers (Rosdiana et al., 2023; Batugal & Tindowen, 2019; Ximenes et al., 2024; Rismawati & Saluy, 2018; Priliantari & Raharja, 2023; Pakpahan et al., 2019).

From the various research results, it is evident that most studies have been conducted in general educational institutions (high schools) or other sectors, and few have explored the impact of teacher competency, transformational leadership of school principals, and organizational culture on teacher performance in pesantren-based Madrasah Aliyah (MA). Although there is research examining the performance of MA teachers, the variables differ from those to be studied by the researcher. For instance, the study by Meliana et al. (2023) examined the transformational leadership of madrasah principals, work discipline, and teacher work motivation on madrasah teacher performance in Banjarmasin, and the study by Rinaldi & Dalle, (2021) focused on the influence of transformational leadership of school principals, work ethic, and achievement motivation on vocational school teacher performance in Banjarmasin. The distinguishing factor in the current study is that it not only focuses on pesantren-based madrasahs but also includes the variable of teacher

competency, which was not examined in the aforementioned studies.

This study aims to analyze (1) the effect of teacher competency on teacher performance; (2) the effect of the transformational leadership style of school principals on teacher performance; (3) the effect of organizational culture on teacher performance; and (4) the combined effect of teacher competency, transformational leadership of school principals, and organizational culture on teacher performance.

II. METHOD

The technique used in this study is the survey technique, and the research method is quantitative. The instrument used in this study is a questionnaire consisting of 20 statement items, with each variable having 5 statements created by the researcher. This research was conducted from July to September 2023. The study was conducted in 2 Madrasah Aliyah (Islamic senior high school) based on pesantren (Islamic boarding school) on Bacan Island, South Halmahera Regency, namely Madrasah Aliyah Darussalam Kupal and Madrasah Aliyah Darul Qur'an Bacan. Data collection was done by distributing questionnaires to all teachers, with a total of 25 teachers, consisting of 15 teachers from MA Darussalam and 10 teachers from MA Darul Qur'an.

III. RESULTS

A. Descriptive Statistics

The data regarding the age, work experience, and level of education of the respondents are tabulated as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Respondent profile

Aspect	Criteria	Total
Age	< 30 years old	14
	30 – 40 years old	9
	41 – 50 years old	2
	> 50 years old	0
Work Experience	< 5 years	15
	5 – 10 years	8
	11 – 20 years	2
	> 20 years	0
Level of Education	S1	25
	S2	0

Respondents under 30 years old amounted to 14 teachers (56%), those aged 30–40 years were 9 teachers (36%), respondents aged 41–50 years were 2 teachers (8%), and there were no teachers over 50 years old. The work experience for each teacher varied, with less than 5 years of work experience accounting for 15 teachers (60%), 5–10 years of work experience for 8 teachers (32%), 11–20 years of work experience for 2 teachers (8%), and no teachers with over 20 years of work experience. Furthermore, all respondents held a bachelor's degree (S1) level of education.

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B. Normality-Test Data

The data obtained through the survey method underwent normality analysis to assess whether the data in a group or variable were normally distributed or drawn from a normal population. After conducting the normality test using Kolmogorov-Smirnov with SPSS version 23 application, the result obtained was 0.073, indicating that the data were normally distributed, as the test result is greater than the probability value of 0.05.

C. Hypothesis Test

Regression Test

For hypotheses 1, 2, and 3, simple linear regression analysis was conducted; and for hypothesis 4, multiple regression analysis was performed with the assistance of SPSS version 23. The results of the analysis can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3. Regression Test Result

Hypothesis	Variable	R ²	F	Beta	t _{test}	sig	Status
H ₁	X ₁ -- Y	0,691	51,317	0,464	7,164	0,00	Accept
H ₂	X ₂ -- Y	0,692	51,792	0,807	7,197	0,00	Accept
H ₃	X ₃ -- Y	0,790	86,576	1,042	9,305	0,00	Accept
H ₄	X ₁ ,X ₂ , X ₃ -- Y	0,915	75,208	0,234	11,381	0,00	Accept

Hypothesis 1: Teacher Competency Has a Positive and Significant Effect on Teacher Performance

The test results for Hypothesis 1 indicate that teacher competency has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance, as evidenced by the regression analysis results: F value = 51.317, β value = 0.4640, t value = 7.164 with p-value < 0.05, and R value = 0.831 with R-square value = 0.691 or 69.1%. The obtained results indicate that teacher competency influences teacher performance by 69.1%, while 30.9% of teacher performance is influenced by factors other than teacher competency. These findings are consistent with the research conducted by Alfredo & Prijanto (2022), which concluded that teacher competency affects teacher performance, meaning that the better the teacher's competency, the better the teacher's performance. Other supporting research includes the study by Halimahturrafiah et al. (2023), stating that teacher competency significantly affects teacher performance, indicating that the higher the competency of a teacher, the higher their performance. Furthermore, the research by Saine et al. (2023) concluded that teacher competency has a significant impact on teacher performance. Similar conclusions are presented by Purba et al. (2018), Wei et al. (2018), and Rahman, M.H (2014). From the research results and the support of various research findings, it can be concluded that an increase in teacher competency will significantly promote an increase in teacher performance, or conversely, if there is a decrease in teacher competency, teacher performance will decrease. Therefore, every teacher is expected to continuously improve their competencies, including pedagogical, professional, personal,

and social competencies, to support optimal performance, especially in the teaching process. Kartini et al. (2020) state that competency is a concept that explains perspectives, understanding, skills, and thought patterns that are valued in relation to a specific job and can be realized through performance in the practice of a specific job.

Hypothesis 2: Transformational Leadership Has a Positive and Significant Effect on Teacher Performance

The second hypothesis explains that transformational leadership has a positive and significant influence on teacher performance. This is evidenced by the regression analysis results: F value = 51.792, β value = 0.897, t value = 7.197 with p-value < 0.05, and R value = 0.832 with R-square value = 0.692 or 69.2%. These test results indicate that the partial influence of transformational leadership on teacher performance is 69.2%, while 30.8% of teacher performance is influenced by factors other than transformational leadership variables. The test results indicate that the transformational leadership of the school principal has a positive influence on the performance of private Islamic high school teachers in Pulau Bacan. This research is supported by Andriani et al. (2018), who concluded that there is a positive and significant influence between transformational leadership and teacher performance, meaning that an increase in transformational leadership is followed by an increase in teacher performance. Similar results are shown by Normianti et al. (2019), stating that the transformational leadership of the school principal influences teacher performance, indicating that teacher performance is influenced by the school principal's leadership style. With a good leadership style by the school principal, it is expected to influence teachers to improve their performance. Similar research findings are found by several researchers including Ginanjar et al. (2022), Meliana, W et al. (2023), and Raharja et al. (2022), concluding that transformational leadership of the school principal influences teacher performance. Teachers have the opportunity to succeed in their teaching tasks if supported by effective school leadership.

Hypothesis 3: Organizational Culture Has a Positive and Significant Effect on Teacher Performance

The analysis results indicate that organizational culture has a positive impact on teacher performance, as evidenced by the test results obtained with F value = 86.576, and probability (p < 0.05), indicating that the regression model created is significant. The coefficient value β = 1.042 indicates that with one unit change in organizational culture, teacher performance will change by 1.042 units. The test result of R value is 0.889 and Rsquare value is 0.790 or 79%, which means the organizational culture has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance by 79%, while 21% of teacher performance is influenced by other factors outside the organizational culture variable. The analysis results show a positive and significant influence between organizational

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culture and teacher performance, as seen from the t value of 9.305. This research is consistent with the study conducted by Ritonga et al. (2023), concluding that organizational culture has a positive effect on teacher performance, meaning that the better the organizational culture, the better the teacher performance. Organizational culture should be created by all members of the madrasah, as a conducive organizational culture will motivate individuals to improve their work, especially in the service provided to students. Organizational culture in a school plays an important role in improving teacher performance (Hatemu, et al., 2020). Furthermore, Tahniah, et al. (2021) state that a positive organizational culture can create a harmonious work environment and promote the improvement of teacher performance. A strong organizational culture will create a sense of trust between teachers and school staff, enabling them to collaborate in building effective learning programs. Meanwhile, Widjajani, (2023) explains that an organizational culture that supports innovation and professional development of teachers can also improve teacher performance in facing new challenges in the field of education.

Hypothesis 4: Teacher Competence, Transformational Leadership, and Organizational Culture Have a Positive and Significant Effect on Teacher Performance

The test results indicate that teacher competence, transformational leadership, and organizational culture together have a positive and significant effect on teacher performance, with an F value of 75.208 and a significance of 0.00, meaning that if teacher competence, transformational leadership of the principal, and organizational culture increase, teacher performance will also increase. The findings align with the research conducted by Alfredo & Prijanto (2022), which states that teacher competence has a positive effect on teacher performance. Lieberman & Miller (2004); and Silitonga et al., (2020) explain that transformational leadership plays a crucial role in fostering a positive organizational culture in schools. Principals can empower teachers by providing opportunities for them to develop their competencies effectively, and creating a sustainable school culture will enhance teacher performance, resulting in improved student learning outcomes. Principals play a crucial role not only in providing tailored teacher competency development but also in fostering a culture that values growth and collaboration.

IV. CONCLUSION

The research conducted in this study focused on four key variables: teacher competence, transformational leadership of the school principal, organizational culture, and teacher performance. The data analysis results indicated that teacher competence has a positive and significant effect on teacher performance. Similarly, the transformational leadership of the school principal also showed a positive and significant impact on teacher performance. Additionally, organizational

culture was found to have a positive and significant influence on teacher performance. Moreover, collectively, teacher competence, transformational leadership, and organizational culture significantly affect teacher performance. Based on these findings, it can be concluded that to enhance teacher performance, school principals should employ leadership styles that engage all teachers in achieving the school's objectives collaboratively. They should also maintain a conducive school culture while continuously improving and developing teacher competence through various professional development activities.

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